

Socio-economic Profile of Two Villages from Rural Areas of Bundelkhand Region: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

The study attempts to study two selected districts randomly from the Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh. One is Banda and the other is Chitrakoot district. Chitrakoot district was carved out from Banda on 6 May 1997 due to ignorance of a few places of Chitrakoot and gun culture prevailed in both regions. From both districts randomly one village from each was selected by the researcher to compare the results. The comparative analysis reflects that Padari village of Chitrakoot Dham is in better condition than Nahari village of Banda district Not only in terms of literacy or agriculture but also in terms of water availability Padari village is far better than Nahari village. Sc population is more in Padari than in Nahari village. ST population is nill in both the villages. number of OBCs are more in both villages.

Keywords Banda, Chitrakoot, Nahari, Padari.

Introduction

About Banda District

The district Banda is getting its name Banda from a Hindu sage Bamdeo. According to Hindu mythology, Bamdeo is known as a contemporary of Rama. The Hermitage of Bamdeo is located at the foot of the hill in this region since then locality has reflected its identity. The study area lies between latitude 24 degrees 53' N and 25 degrees 55' N and longitude 80 degrees 7' east to 81 degrees 34' east. It is bounded by the district of Fatehpur in the North and the district of Allahabad in the east, in the west by the district of Hamirpur, and in the south by the Rewa, Panna, Satna, and Chhatarpur districts of Madhya Pradesh. Banda district covered a 4408 sq km area (<https://banda.nic.in>; 05/07/2020, 09:28 AM). According to the 2011 census, the total population of this area is 199,812,341. It is an increase of 20.2% from the previous year 2001. 77.7% population of the total population is rural. From the previous year, the rural population increased by 22.3% in this district.

Figure No. 1.3: Map of Banda District

